

Social

EMERGING ECONOMETRICS OF BOMB, WAR AND FREE DIRECT INVESTMENTS TO STABILIZE THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF OWN COUNTRY IN GLOBALIZED WORLD

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Abstract

The global economy has been facing a lot of challenges and crisis due to Interlinkage for exchanging goods and services. A race is going on among different nations to become a super powerful country. As a result of which global warming and climate change has been seen throughout the world. A new econometrics has taken over the charge of international politics and that could be seen in the recent developments took place in Korean Peninsula and some part of the world where powerful politicians of the world have been threatening to each other for deep consequences.

The Key Questions are,

Q.1. What happened in the Middle East?

Q.2. What is happening in Syria and others countries?

Ans. The impact would be more transparent and visible in the coming days.

Q.3. What is OBOR (One Belt One Road) of China?

Ans. Imposing their excess burdens on other countries on the name of globalization and peace building and making realize the participating countries that you are under my kindness with liabilities(indirect loan).

The present paper has tried to find out answers of some questions and also suggests solutions at last. Qualitative thinking is always better than quantitative thinking.

Keywords: Econometrics; Globalization; Peace Building; War; ROI; Sustainable Development; Vasudhaiv Kuttumbakam.

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1. Introduction

Econometrics is basically concerned with statistical implication of economics for forecasting future trends and testing various models through mathematical interpretation or trials and then compare/contrast it against real life situations in prevailing economic conditions of a country. In one line it is calculation based thinking (worldly affairs).

The new econometrics has been developed by some of the great politicians of the world and other has to follow the same, if they are in the race of procuring weapons of mass destruction and surplus production of goods without considering environmental degradation. And all these measures would be to improve collapsed economy of their own country without taking into account of Impact on neighbor or other countries. A live example of this can be seen in the world when a developed country equipped with overloaded war equipment, surplus goods, surplus manufacturing industries and superb technologies starts suffering with economic crisis, unemployment, social conflicts and other injustice to people and nature, then these countries starts teasing and interfering into the economy of other countries for taking ROI (Return On Investment) to improve their own economy as they know, simply by taking some good steps within the country would be of no use because economy is globalized now. Hence, do somewhere else, in some other country and take benefits of doubts. The most important thing is that these developed countries have no more good things to give to the world except weapons of mass destruction, corrupt political system, negative use of technology, global warming and climate change, which they procured and produced during the last five to ten decades to become a powerful country of the world and finding market for their excessively produced unsold goods to be sold at cheaper price (cost price). And now all these weapons, equipment, negative technology, and unfriendly goods are reaching to their expiry dates, so the only option left is to dispose it in other countries before it reached the expiry date and to take the maximum benefits out of its impact in the form of war, silk rout, political instability, degrading socio-economic conditions and disrupting peace. These days almost all countries in the fast moving world are linked with each other for exchanging goods and services, so bombing on one country will give reverse impact on many other countries and at last it will come to own country as ROI, "*that will further help in overcoming with economic crisis and stabilizing the economy of my countries*" is the general thinking of some of the current politicians. Connect other countries by investing money in developing infrastructure for transportation of our surplus goods/technology for increasing consumption in these countries and imposing burden of loan (indirect way) is the other thinking.

And before doing all this, it is decided by politicians to find out the cluster of countries which has potential to give reverse ROI impact. And then decision would be taken to create political disturbances in and around that country by provoking for war and other social issues or else extending offers of heavy investment in such countries.

The new econometrics has two major elements. Those are,

- 1) "War" and "Bomb" to control and provoke to action
- 2) Free Investment in Infrastructure Development (FIID) particularly in the areas of transportation.

Initially FIID seems like a mouthwatering offer that could not be restricted because of freeness but later on works like sweet poison that would have tendency to engulf the whole economy of any country where it persists.

It would be of great use if all such econometrics have “selfless” base and would consider world as one family.....

World has witnessed many people come and go that represent this.

“Help if you can always - Even if you cannot help – Do no harm”

Purana(great epics/scriptures of India) also says(in Sanskrit Language),

*“Astadasa Puranesu Vyasena Vachanam Dwayam,
Paropakarayaya Punyaya – Papaya Para Peedanam”*

It means essence of 18 puranas is “helping others is punya (good/blessings of God) and hurting others is papa(evil/sin)”. “Make a difference with your presence”. Our presence should bring in a positive change in the place or people. This should be the case in all places, in all times, in all circumstances. Attitude of gratitude help us connect and experience our blessings.

2. Experience Connectedness (Indian Philosophy)

We are not alone. We are connected to everything and everyone in the universe. Experience this connectivity.

“Vasudhaiv Kuttumbakam” (World is one Family)

This is the true world wide web (www). Any thought word, action by any one of us has an impact to the totality of universe. As for the law of transformation of energy, the sum total of energy in the universe is constant. It can neither be created nor destroyed and it can only be transformed from one state to another. This applies to all our thoughts, all our words and actions. So we are connected to everybody and to everything in the universe. One should be careful on what they think, say or do. One should think positive, speak positive and do positive things. This experience of connectedness is Visvaroop Darshan or realization. This is also called Constant Integrated Awareness (CIA). Experience the Oneness, we are.

“Sacrifice the Limitedness”. Ahankar (ego) is the mind’s identification with the limited body. Thyaga is sacrifice. True sacrifice is, sacrifice of our limitedness, so that we expand into unlimitedness (infinite). This is what the Upanishads mean when they declared “Thyagenaike Amrutatva Manasu – Only through sacrifice one attains immortality”. Selfless Service is a good vehicle to expand to our full potential through sacrifice of ego. This is the final frontier in the journey towards self-realization. Serve All. Sacrifice what you are not (ego) and be what you really (atma) are, your true self (Atma).

The following quotation in Sanskrit from ancient Indian Scripture that tell us to leave in eternal peace always.

ॐ सर्वे भवन्तु सुखिनः (Om Sarve Bhavantu Sukhinah)

सर्वे सन्तु निरामयाः (Sarve Santu Nir-Aamayaah)

सर्वे भद्राणि पश्यन्तु (Sarve Bhadraanni Pashyanttu)

मा कश्चिद्दुःखभागभवेत् (Maa Kashcid-Duhkha-Bhaag-Bhaves)

ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः (Om Shaantih Shaantih Shaantih)

Meaning

- 1) Om(Hey God !), May All become Happy,
- 2) May All be Free from Illness.
- 3) May All See what is Auspicious,
- 4) May no one Suffer.
- 5) Om(Hey God!) Grace all with Peace, Peace and Peace

The above quotation of ancient time is now more applicable to fight against global warming and climate change by spreading peace and harmony among people but it would only be possible if, everyone in this world give respect and honour to each other i.e. living and non-living both. And no doubt in this that age old indigenous culture, scriptures, epics and great philosophical thoughts of ancient philosophers are still applicable, implementable and alive and would be alive till the existence of the world through its successors.

3. Conclusion

Eternal peace building among human beings can only help to fight against economic crisis, global warming and climate change and would further help in regaining the lost wealth/ROI. People need to learn how to satisfy their unlimited wants with limited resources available to them in their surroundings. And in this process indigenous cultural methods and doctrines of great philosophers can contribute maximum to human for getting eternal peace. Experience this connectivity. We are connected to everybody and to everything in the universe. One should be careful on what they think, say or do. One should think positive, speak positive and do positive things in sustainable way.

4. Limitations of Existing Study

Any generalized idea is not right due to variations in size, goal, changing perceptions and region and literatures followed.

5. Scope of Research

The further research must direct itself for conducting such investigations. This will make the study more meaningful to find linkage more effectively. Further the suggested statements need to be tested for its authenticity across the destinations and benchmarks to be identified for others to

follow. Further the views suggested are macroscopic; this can be further extended to microscopic level.

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